

STUDIES ON THE COMPOSITION OF PEPTONE. PART IV.

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Anhydride and lactam formation or deamination can take place to a certain extent during protein hydrolysis depending on the concentration of hydrochloric acid used. In the analysis of peptone, which generally contains aggregates of a small number of amino-acids, occurrence of these side reactions may significantly affect the results. Hydrolysis with 3N.HCl is found to give best results than acids of other strength.

Determination of the increase in the number of carboxyl groups, amino and imino groups furnishes an experimental means of ascertaining the number of peptide bonds present in a given weight of protein. This increase further shows the number of amino-acids that aggregate together to form the protein molecule. From this average weight of protein containing one mole of peptide bond can be calculated. A protein containing larger amount of lighter amino-acids will have relatively low weight per bond and the reverse will be the case when it contains heavier amino-acids. These results will depend on the characteristics and composition of the protein.

This type of calculation is, however, strictly correct only when the number of peptide bonds is equal to the amino-acids residue obtained after complete hydrolysis. Correction has to be made for the carboxyl group due to amide, but still there remains a source of error due to some side reactions during the process of hydrolysis. Working with a low concentration of hydrochloric acid, anhydride and lactam formations have been observed by various workers with amino-acids and protein hydrolysate (Zelinski and Sadikov, *Biochem. Z.*, 1923, 138, 156; Wilson and Cannan, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1937, 119, 309; Gavrilov *et al.*, *Bull. soc., Chim.*, 1938, 5, 442). On the other hand Kossel and Kutscher (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1900, 31, 165) and Hotchkiss (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1933, 131 387) observed that deamination of amino-acids takes place to a certain extent in presence of comparatively strong hydrochloric acid at a high temperature. Corrections due to these side reactions are of negligible consequence in case of proteins which contain several hundreds of amino-acids residues, but in case of peptones¹, which contain aggregates of a few amino-acids, these reactions are of serious consequences in the interpretation of the results.

The following investigation was undertaken with the object of finding up to what extent different acid concentrations affect the results of hydrolysis and of finding out a method of peptone analysis with the least chance of error.

EXPERIMENTAL

Bacto peptone solutions (5%) were made with 6N, 3N and N-hydrochloric acid. Each solution (200 c.c.) was heated with a reflux condenser in an oil bath at 120° to 125° for 10 hours. The hydrolysate (10 c.c.) was taken at different intervals, major portion of HCl in it was removed in vacuum and the volume made up to 10 c.c.

with conductivity water. Carboxyl groups were determined in 2 c.c. hydrolysate by titration with alcoholic potassium hydroxide with thymolphthalein as indicator and values corrected for retained hydrochloric acid by Volhard method using nitric acid as oxidising agent. Increase in carboxyl group was corrected for ammonia (Sen, *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1942, 30, 335). The following calculations were made. (a) 1 mole of CONH \equiv 1 mole of KOH \equiv 1 \times 10⁴ c.c. of 0.1N KOH, or i.e.c. of 0.1N KOH \equiv 1 \times 10⁻⁴ moles CONH. Hence the increase in COOH (on complete hydrolysis) in multiples of 1 c.c. of 0.1N-KOH for initial acidity to each c.c. of 0.1N-KOH gives the moles of peptide bonds present. This is converted into nearest whole number. (b) Weight of peptone per mole of peptide linkage was calculated from the weight that would be equivalent to one mole of KOH on complete hydrolysis. (c) Average residual weight per peptide bond was calculated by deducting the weight of peptone which is present as free amino-acids (equivalent to initial free COOH groups) from the total weight of peptone containing one mole of peptide bond. Results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Concentration of HCl	Increase in COOH equivalent to c.c. of 0.1N-KOH per 100 mg. peptone at					Number of peptide bonds per protein molecule (average).	Initial free COOH as % of total COOH.	Peptone per mole of peptide.	Average weight per peptide bond.	
	1	2	5	7	10					
6N	(a)	4.70	5.76	6.24	6.24	6.24	3	25.0	160.g.	120.0
	(b)	4.80	5.80	6.30	6.30	6.30				
	(c)	4.75	5.78	6.24	6.24	6.26				
	(d)	4.75	5.80	6.26	6.26	6.26				
3N	(a)	4.48	5.88	7.38	7.40	7.39	4	22.0	149.2	116.4
	(b)	4.50	5.88	7.34	7.40	7.40				
	(c)	4.50	5.88	7.34	7.41	7.40				
	(d)	4.55	5.84	7.37	7.38	7.40				
1N	(a)	2.96	4.54	5.62	6.26	6.26	3	24.0	160.0	121.6
	(b)	3.00	4.54	5.68	6.26	6.26				
	(c)	2.96	4.60	5.71	6.30	6.31				
	(d)	2.94	4.54	5.70	6.26	6.31				

Initially 100 mg. of peptone (2.0 c.c. of 5.0% solution) was equivalent to 1.94 c.c. 1N-KOH.

Since in the hydrolysis of peptide bonds carboxyl and amino groups are liberated in equivalent amount, the ratio of these two increases will be constant. In case the peptide linkage contains a proline residue, the breakdown of the bond will liberate an imino-group and Van Slyke amino-nitrogen figure will correspondingly diminish. In case there is any anhydride or lactam formation, the amount of COOH will proportionately diminish. At each interval as above, amino-nitrogen was determined by Van Slyke's (gasometric) method after removal of ammonia. Carboxyl groups were converted into amino-nitrogen (1 c.c. of 0.1N-KOH \equiv 1.4 mg. of amino-N). The ratio of these two increases at different intervals is shown in Fig. 1.

FIG. 1.

DISCUSSION.

Decrease in the ratio of COOH (in equivalent to amino-nitrogen) and Van Slyke's amino-N has been observed with 1N-HCl after showing an increase for a few hours (Fig. 1.) This decrease may be due either to a decrease in available COOH or to an increase in amino-N. Increase in amino-N out of proportion to COOH groups is not compatible with our present knowledge of protein structure which essentially consists of peptide linkage (Pauling and Niemann, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 1860). The other alternative is unavailability of COOH under experimental condition. If this is due to the combination between α -NH₂ group and COOH group, as in the case of lactam formation with glutamic acid, the ratio would not have altered. But if the combination is between COOH and NH₂ group, other than at α position, a decrease in the ratio is apparent. An internal combination in lysine between ϵ -NH₂ and COOH groups can take place as observed by Adamson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 39). Similar combination between ϵ -NH₂ group of lysine and COOH group of other amino-acids is also possible. Side reaction with 1N-HCl takes place after certain time. This is probably due to the decrease in effective acid concentration as the ampholytic concentration increases with hydrolysis. The maximum number of peptide linkage hydrolysed together with a high COOH/NH₂-N ratio suggests that with 3N-HCl minimum side reactions take place. Significant difference in the results is also exhibited when other figures are calculated from the data in Table I. Average weight per peptide bond as obtained here is in good agreement with the similar results (115.5) given in literature (Bergmann and Niemann, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1937, 118, 301). This average residual weight can be taken to be equal to the weight of hypothetical amino-acid residue but this is true only when the number of peptide linkage is large compared with the number of free terminal COOH groups. On the basis of four peptide linkage per mole of peptone (Table I), weight of amino-acids calculated from average residual weight (116.4 + 18) and that calculated from average weight per peptide bond $\frac{(116.4 \times 4}{5} + 18)$ exhibits a difference of about 20.0%.

From the figures so far obtained, it appears that best results are obtained with 3N-HCl in case of peptone hydrolysis. Complete hydrolysis takes place within 5 to 6 hours at 120-125°. Further heating for a few hours more does not affect the results.